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MERGERS, ACQUISITIONS AND THE IMPERATIVE OF A COMPETITION POLICY IN NIGERIA^{1*}

Abstract

This paper examines mergers and acquisitions as a veritable tool for corporate and industrial growth particularly in Nigeria. To this end, this paper is treated in five parts.

Part one examines the concept of mergers and acquisitions while part two treats the various forms of business combinations. Part three examines the arguments for and against mergers and acquisitions while part four analyses the legal and institutional framework for regulation of mergers and acquisitions deals. The last part that is part five examines the theory, policy and law of competition. This paper concludes by arguing that a competition regime is necessary so as to soften the social impact of mergers and acquisitions.

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MERGERS, ACQUISITIONS AND THE IMPERATIVE OF A COMPETITION POLICY IN NIGERIA*

Introduction

Until recently when the idea of mergers and acquisitions came into focus in Nigeria as a result of the failures of several financial institutions and the call by the regulatory authorities for a higher capital base to ensure the stability and viability of financial institutions the idea was merely of academic importance.²

These, in addition to the country's changing economic fortunes and the various austerity and restructuring programmes which government has tried to implement have compelled individuals and corporate bodies to embark on various restructuring programme and diversification operations as regards their businesses so as to ensure survival and growth.

Thus, there were merger deals between Lever Brothers (Nig) PLC and Chesebrough Products Industries Ltd, Lipton (Nig) Ltd and Unilever Nigeria Ltd as well as the fusion of Sterling Products and Smithkline Beecham.³ There were also merger deals between some government financial institutions such as Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB), Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI) and Nigerian Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) on one hand and Peoples Bank of Nigeria (PBN) and Nigerian Agricultural and Co - operative Bank (NAIB) on the

² One of the earliest few cases of mergers and acquisitions was that of Re Bendel Line. Company Limited where the scheme for sanction was that Bendel Line Company Limited and Transklife Limited be amalgamated under a new company known as Bendel Transport Services Limited. This scheme predates the SEC of 1982.

³ See Re Smithkline Beecham Nig. Plc, Suit No. FHC/L/CS/901/96 unreported judgment of the Federal High Court Lagos. In this merger between Sterling Products (Nig.) Plc with Smithkline Beecham Plc U.K over 60% of Sterling's shares were beneficiary, held by Sterling Products International Limited, a wholly owned subsidiary of Smithkline Beecham Plc U.K. The same Smithkline Beecham Plc U.K, through another wholly owned subsidiary called Beecham Group Nig. Plc, held 40% of the shares of Smithkline Beecham Nig. Plc. Apart from the fact that both companies had a common parent in Smithkline Beecham Plc. U.K, both engaged in the manufacture, marketing and distribution of various pharmaceuticals, over - the - counter medicines and consumer health care products. The merger would no doubt benefit both in the area of management, finance, manufacturing and marketing.

other hand. The expectation was that the merger of these government's financial institutions will, as with other cases of acquisition deals lead to the streamlining of their operations, make them more efficient as wastages and inadequacies caused by their individual operations will be eliminated or at least curtailed. Above all, it will remove duplication of functions of these organizations.

One hopes also that their merger would stop the wastages of public funds on them without any commensurate return on investment. This paper examines the practice of mergers and acquisitions as a veritable tool for corporate and industrial growth particularly in Nigeria. The paper is divided into five parts. Part one examines the concepts of mergers and acquisitions while part two treats the various forms of business combinations. Part three considers the arguments for and against mergers and acquisitions while part four analyses the legal and institutional frame work for the regulation of mergers and acquisitions deals. Then part five examines competition theory, policy and law. The paper concluded by arguing that mergers and acquisition should be carried out in a bid to enhance the competitiveness of a company. The consumer should be the main beneficiary. Competition policy is necessary therefore to soften the social impact of the mergers and acquisitions.

1. The Concept of Mergers and Acquisitions

One of the rising growth strategies in contemporary industrial cooperation of the world is the merger of business organizations.⁴ This is the binding together of hitherto

⁴ A prominent feature of this phenomenon is the existence of multinationals whose activities span many national borders in various fields of commerce and industry. This development has been attributed in the main to various mergers and acquisitions schemes across the globe. Recent mergers across the world include those of Royal/Shell BP, Amoco/Arco, Exxon/Mobil and Total/Petrofina in the oil industry; Glaxo Wellcome and Smithklines Beecham in the pharmaceutical sector and the merger between KLM Royal Dutch Airlines and Alitalia (Italian Airlines) in the sphere of Aviation. The product of the merger between the United Kingdom - Based Glaxo Wellcome and Smithkline Beecham both of which are very strong operators in the pharmaceutical sector, Glaxo Smithkline, valued at 130 billion pounds sterling (about N20.849 trillion) will expectedly bestride the UK's corporate world. Under the deal, Glaxo's shareholders will own 58.75 % of Glaxo Smithkline, while their counterparts in Smithkline will own 41.25 %. But to demonstrate the spirit of give and take embedded in such arrangement, the newly formed company had Jean - pierre Gamle, who then hold the number two position in Smithkline as the chief executive , while Glaxo Wellcome's steersman , Sir Richard Sykes , become the non - executive chairman . It then means that the candidate of the minority party in the arrangement became the chief executive while the majority stakeholders had the non - executive chairmanship

independent industrial outfits with the aim of optimizing their comparative strengths and achieving synergy. As products of economic realities and as a contemporary growth strategy mergers and acquisitions emphasize the synergy⁵ of resources for maximum profitability. The focal point of mergers and acquisitions is to maximize returns in the areas where the merging companies have comparative advantages. This theory, which is associated with division of labour engenders trade co - operation, and in international circles is called comparative advantage principle of international trade.

Synergy aims at achieving improved marketing strategies and effective resource - utilization through the harnessing of the combined strengths of the merged organizations. It brings about improved capital gains in investment and profitability which result from increased business activity.

Even though mergers and acquisitions are often used interchangeably to describe forms of business combinations, other terms such as take over, re - organisation, amalgamation, reconstruction, schemes of arrangements⁶, compromise, combination and consolidation have also been used in describing one form of business combination or the other. It seems however, that reconstruction, reorganization or scheme of arrangement are expressions employed when the rights of the company's investors and

post. Other highlights show that as a result of the merger, the parties in the deal will be saving 250 million pounds sterling (N40.095 billion) on their research and development expenditure. The new company's sales volume is expected to hit 17 billion pounds.

⁵ Synergy has many connotations. In the area of theology, it is the doctrine, which states that the human will co - operate with Divine Grace in the work of regeneration. In the field of medicine, synergy involves the combined or correlated action of a group of bodily organs (such as nerve centres, muscles etc.). In the economic context however, it is the Interaction of discrete agencies or agents such that the total effect is greater than the individual effects. Economically, synergy creates a glant firm with capabilities and prospects, which are larger than the aggregate of what the individual units could have produced if they operated separately. It entails removing the areas of weakness in one and diluting them with the strong points in the other to create a more resilient and focused product. See Olugbemi Fatula; Mergers and Acquisitions; being a paper in chapter 3 of the book: Fundamentals of Nigerian Company Law and Administration, L & B Publishers (2nd edition) 2004 at P. 150.

⁶ According to Geoffrey Morse, the word arrangement has a very wide meaning, and is wider than the word compromise. An arrangement may involve debenture holders giving an extension of time for payment, accepting a cash payment less than the face value of their debentures, giving up their security in whole or in part, exchanging their debentures for shares in the company or in a new company or having the rights attached to their debentures varied in some other respect. See Charlesworth and Morse: Company Law; 15th Edition by Geoffrey Morse, Sweet & Maxwell, 1996 at p. 810-811.

sometimes of its general creditors are varied. On the other hand, amalgamation, merger or takeover or acquisitions are employed when two or more companies are involved either de jure by a consolidation of their undertakings, or de facto by the acquisition of a controlling interest in the share capital of one by the other or the capital of both by a new company.⁷

The term merger is not defined in the Investment and Securities Act (ISA) No. 45 of 1999.⁸ Under the Companies and Allied Matters Act 1990 (CAMA)⁹, merger is defined to mean any amalgamation of the undertakings or any part of the undertakings of one or more companies and one or more bodies corporate¹⁰. Acquisition, unlike mergers is not defined by the repealed Companies Decree¹¹, CAMA or ISA but the definition of takeover is close to acquisition¹². Takeover under ISA means the acquisition by one company of sufficient shares in another company as to give the acquiring company control over the other company¹³.

A takeover has also been defined as:

"An offer to acquire shares of a company whose shares are not closely held, addressed to the general body of shareholders, with a

⁷ See LC.B. Gower, Principles of Modern Company Law 5 ed: (Sweet & Maxwell) 1992 p . 689

⁸ Hereinafter called ISA.

⁹ Hereinafter called CAMA.

¹⁰ See section 590 CAMA.

¹¹ 1968 Companies Decree.

¹² There has been attempt to distinguish between acquisitions and take - over. Acquisitions is said to be a situation where a stronger company acquires the controlling Interests in the share capital of a presumably weaker company to assume a good measure of control. The acquired company would usually retain its name but remains a subsidiary of the acquiring company. Unlike in mergers and acquisitions, take - over usually involve the total take - over by a stronger company of a weaker and dying company. This calls for the assumption of full control, ownership or management of one company by another. In virtually all cases of take-over, the companies being taken over are distressed, with the buying companies inheriting the liabilities of the distressed companies with the hope of revamping or turning them around. See Steve Omojfor, Mergers, Acquisitions, Take - overs and Affiliation: which way forward for the advertising indus try, The Comet, Friday, January 9, 2004 at p. 16.

¹³ See Section 99 (1) ISA. See also Section 590 CAMA.

view to obtaining at least sufficient shares to give the offeror voting control of the company"¹⁴.

An essential difference therefore between a merger and an acquisition is that unlike acquisition, in the absence of any dissenting Shareholder there is no dis - investment of the Shareholders of the amalgamating companies.

2. Conceptual Analysis of Forms of Business Combinations

Variations of types of mergers and acquisitions are often categorized as Vertical, Horizontal and Conglomerate.¹⁵ A strategy of vertical integration means that a company is producing its own inputs (backward or upstream integration) or disposing of its own outputs (forward or downward integration). A steel company that combines with Iron Ore Mine Company for its ore needs exemplifies backward (upstream) integration.¹⁶ The basic objective of vertical merger is to have a steady supply of input or outlet for products or services.¹⁷ Horizontal integration happens where a firm takes over or merges with a company in the same industry and at almost the same level in that industry. It has been postulated that companies pursue horizontal mergers so as to obtain economy of scale or to secure a national market for their product. As a result, they are able to pursue a cost leadership or a differentiation strategy or both. Horizontal combinations tend to decrease the number of firms in an industry, making it easier for them to collude for monopoly profit and anti - competitive practices.

¹⁴ M.A Weinberg and M.V. Blank, *Take Overs and Mergers*. 4th ed. London, (Sweet and Maxwell) (1979), p. 4.

¹⁵ See P.A Farrar & P.B.M Hamigan: *Farrars Company Law*, 4th edition; Butterworth Publishers, p. 43. See also Rogers D. Blair and David L. Kaseman, *Antitrust Economics*, London Butterworth (1995) pp. 227-228.

¹⁶ Vertical mergers occur between firms in different stages of production where the merging firms have a customer/supplier relationship or engages in complementary business activities. See Wole Adetunji "Roles of Regulating Institutions in Mergers and Acquisitions" NIALS, May 15, 1998 p. 4.

¹⁷ The merger between Nestle Nig . Ltd. & Nestle Foods Nig. Plc. illustrate this type of merger. See *Re Nestle Nig. Ltd. and Nestle Foods Nig. Plc*, Suit No. FHC/L/CS/745/96. Unreported judgement of the Federal High Court, Lagos.

There is thus the need to always subject them to controls regulations.¹⁸

Conglomerate integration is just an expansion of the firm into fields that are unrelated to the existing interests of the firm. There is no increased concentration in any one field, as would occur in the horizontal mergers and no new control of inputs or outputs as it would occur in the vertical merger. There is just an increased concentration of total economic activity in all fields. Conglomerate mergers are often motivated by the desire to diversify so as to reduce risk and maximize profits.¹⁹

3. Arguments for and Against Mergers and Acquisitions

a. Arguments in favour of Mergers and Acquisitions

For Companies hitherto separate and independent to come together to form one company definitely there must be some benefits envisaged.

Firstly, the synergistic effects on business combinations have made many companies to adopt the strategy as a means of overcoming their problems and to consolidate their positions. Synergy will result in substantial trade advantage or greater profit than the combined profit of the two companies working separately.²⁰

Secondly, mergers and acquisitions are an effective and comparatively gentle tool for reshaping an economic structure in response to fundamentally new conditions, such as restructuring the production apparatus or building broader networks for innovations²¹.

Thirdly, mergers and acquisitions are a relatively gentle way of bringing the structure of an economy in line with fundamental changes in global markets and new

¹⁸ See Wole Adetunji: Op. Cit at p. 2. The acquisition of American Motors by Chrysler represented a horizontal combination or mergers. The merger of Sapanda Industries Ltd. & Nigerian Bottling Company Plc is horizontal. See *Re Nigerian Bottling Co. Plc & Sapanda Industries Ltd.* Suit No. FHC/L/CS/1030/96. Unreported judgement of the Federal High Court, Lagos.

¹⁹ J.F.W Weston has distinguished between three types of conglomerate mergers namely: Product extension mergers, Geographical market extension mergers and Pure conglomerate mergers. See 1. Fred Weston; *Take Overs, Restructuring and Corporate Governance* 2nd ed. (New Jersey; Prentice - Hall Int. 1988) p. 6.

²⁰ This is normally mathematically expressed thus: $2 + 2 = 5$

²¹ See Helmut O. Maucher; *Mergers and acquisitions as a means of restructuring and repositioning in the global market : business , macro - economic and political aspects , being an article view in Transnational Corporations*, vol.7, no. 3 (December 1998) at p. 153.

technological challenges. Such an adjustment incorporates Joseph Schumpeter's creative destruction of obsolete ideas and structures in order to create new combinations of productive capacities. Bankruptcy would be the usual and very costly way of destruction²². Mergers and acquisitions allow large parts of existing resources, including the employees of companies with their knowledge and expertise to be retained. These resources are regrouped and optimized in this restructuring phase²³.

Fourthly, the combination of businesses has also become imperative in order to achieve economy of scale and a robust corporate growth. Companies typically use acquisition to enter a business area that is new to them. When a company lacks the wherewithal or competencies (resources and capabilities) required to complete an industry but has fund to purchase an incumbent company that has those competencies, acquisition is advisable.

Companies also have a preference for acquisitions as an entry mode when they feel the need to move fast. In general, building a new business through internal venturing can be a relatively slow process but in contrast acquisition is a much quicker way to establish a significant market presence and generate profitability.

A company can purchase a market leader in a strong cash position overnight, rather than spend years building up a market-leadership position through internal development. Thus, when speed is important, acquisition is the favoured entry mode.

Furthermore, acquisitions are also often perceived to be somewhat less risky than internal new ventures primarily because they involve less uncertainty. Due to the nature of internal new ventures, large uncertainties are associated with projecting future profitability, revenues and cash flows. In contrast, when a company makes an acquisition, it is acquiring known profitability, known revenues and known market share, all of which reduce uncertainty. It has been observed that acquisition allows a

²² Schumpeter, Joseph A. *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy* (New York: Harper). 1942

²³ Helmut O. Maucher; Op cit at p. 155.

company to buy an established business with a track record, and for this reason many companies favour acquisitions as a method of entry into new business areas.²⁴

Again, acquisitions may be preferred entry modes when the industry to be entered is well established and incumbent enterprises enjoy significant protection from barriers to entry. Apparently, barriers to entry arise from factors associated with product differentiation (brand loyalty), absolute cost advantages, and economies of scale. When such barriers are substantial, a company finds entering an industry through internal venturing difficult. To enter, a company may have to construct an efficient - scale manufacturing plant, undertake massive advertising to break down established brand loyalties, and quickly build up distribution outlets. All these are goals that are hard to achieve and likely to involve substantial expenditures. In contrast, a company can circumvent most barriers to entry. It can purchase a market leader, which already benefits from substantial economies of scale and brand loyalty. Thus, the greater the barriers to entry, the most likely it is that acquisitions will be the favoured entry mode.

Corporations may embark on pure conglomerate merger so as to guard against possible business failure associated with monocultural line of business. Mergers enable easy diversification into new line of businesses. Mergers and diversified companies become too big to be taken over or acquired by another enterprise.

The desire to qualify for a stock exchange listing, by private companies may make it merge with a publicly quoted company. Again, a technologically and manpower deficient company desirous of enhancing its operation may merge with a technologically advanced company with requisite manpower.

Other reasons include, economies of scales resulting from enhanced capacity utilization due to increased market share.

b. Arguments against Mergers and Acquisitions

Acquisitions have been a popular vehicle for expanding the scope of organizations into new business areas. However, despite this popularity there is ample evidence that

²⁴ Canella, A.A and Hambrick, D.C (1993), "Executive Departure and Acquisition Performance". Strategic Management Journal, pp 137-152.

many acquisitions fail to add value for the acquiring company and indeed often end up dissipating value. More generally, there is a wealth of evidence from experience that many acquisitions fail to realize their anticipated benefits. This is as a result of inadequate pre - acquisition screening, post - acquisition integration problem, false assumption that merger or acquisition is an alternative to organic growth after periods of downsizing, restructuring and re-engineering, organizations cultural differences, prospects and problems of developing new strategic concepts and implementation plans, etc.²⁵

Again, inspite of the benefits of mergers to integrating companies in terms of enhanced fortunes, it is necessary to have mergers controlled because of the undesirable consequences that might result from activities of the integrated companies. One of these has been termed externalities. And of these, pollution is the most commonly cited. Another undesirable consequence is monopoly. Monopolists are known to have a tendency to engage in anticompetitive practices that are detrimental to the larger society. Such practices would include predatory pricing, horizontal agreements among firms in the same market to fix prices or prohibit entry as well as vertical agreements between a supplier and customer in the areas of retail price maintenance, exclusive dealing, territorial exclusivity, quantity discounts, tie in sales and long-term supply contracts. According to Adam Smith prices tend to be cheaper in a regime of competition than in a monopoly²⁶ regime where the whole trade is monopolized by one or two firms.²⁷

²⁵ Olugbemi Fatula (ed) Fundamentals of Nigerian Company Law and Administration: L & B publishers, Lagos, 2000 at pp. 112 & 113

²⁶ Monopolies can be loosely described as markets in which one firm or a group of firms acting together establish a dominant position. If the monopoly is making excess profit or is inefficient, then the obvious remedies are either to break it up to restore the competitive outcome or to regulate prices, at the same time seeking to promote efficiency. The latter solution is typically applied in industries which are perceived as being 'natural monopolies' i.e. industries where economies of scale and scope are so large that production is carried on most cheaply by a single firm. Such industries are typically public utilities relying on networks of wires and pipes to distribute their products, and in most Western countries special arrangements are made to regulate them, normally through price controls. Industries which are not natural monopolies only requires the introduction of some degree of competition rather than regulation. In such cases, breaking up the monopoly is an attractive approach to the abuse of monopoly power. See the introductory part of the book

Mergers and acquisitions and restructuring measures affect people many have to get used to different structures at their place of work, many have to relocate to a new town, some take early retirement and often people are laid off. Even if it all serves to secure jobs over the long term, the fate of individuals must be kept in mind. It is in the clear interests of the company to ensure an effective programme of social measures geared at softening the impact of restructuring measures²⁸.

4. The Legal / Regulatory Framework of Mergers and Acquisition in Nigeria

The Federal government's efforts in reforming, modernizing and Internationalizing the Nigerian capital market began way back in 1993 with the deregulation of securities pricing in the primary market.²⁹ The setting up in 1996, of a 7 member Panel headed happens by Dennis Odife to review the Nigerian Capital Market was undeniably a positive step in further pursuits of government determination to properly position the market to face the challenges of the coming millennium.³⁰ With the report of this 7 man panel, a new law, the Investment and Securities Act No. 45 of 1999 whose provisions align in purpose and intention with other pronouncements by government was promulgated in May 1999. The Act,³¹ whose provisions conform with international standard practices is an all-embracing document³², giving enlarged functions and wide powers to the Security and Exchange Commission to administering securities law in Nigeria. The Act, among other things, has repealed The Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Issue of Non-Voting Equity Shares Decree 1990, the Security and Exchange Commission Decree 1988, Part XVII of the CAMA 1990

Competition and Competition Policy, by Martin Cave and Saul Estrin, Printer Publishers Ltd, (UK) 1993, at pp. 2-3

²⁷ Adam Smith: *An Inquiry into the Nature and causes of the Wealth of Nations* R.H. Campbell et al. (ed.) London, Oxford Press, (1976), p. 76.

²⁸ Helmut O. Maucher; *Op. Cit* at p. 168.

²⁹ Olugbemi Fatula (ed.) *Op. Ct* at p. 117.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ Investment and Security Act 45 of 1999; hereinafter referred to as 1.5.A. 999.

³² O. Fatula: *Op. 117.*

as well as Section 21 (2) of the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission Decree 1995.³³

(a) Procedures for Mergers and Acquisition

The procedure for the strict merger of two or more companies are provided in section 99 to 102 of ISA while that of Takeover are provided in sections 103 to 122 of the same Act.

1. Take - over Procedures

Though, as earlier noted, both terms are normally interchangeably used, takeover differs from merger and any other form of reconstruction methods because in strict Law, the company that is being taken over does not itself participate in the process. What happen is that one company (or an individual bidder) makes an offer to the shareholders of another to buy their shares either for cash, or for its own shares or debentures, or for a mixture of both. Such offer is expressed to be conditional on acceptance by a stated proportion of shareholders in such a way that those accepting became bound to sell but the offeror does not become bound to buy until the condition is fulfilled. If as a result, the acquiring company obtains a controlling interest in the company to be taken over, the latter will become a subsidiary of the former. Takeover normally arises where the bidding company may desire to acquire the control of another which is ripe for takeover because its shares for one reason or another are quoted much below the actual or potential value of its business. If the consideration was shares in the acquiring company, the shareholders in the taken over company will become shareholders in the acquiring company. Takeover bids are regulated by section 103 to 122 of ISA. A bid for takeover cannot be made by any person or persons unless an authority to proceed with takeover has been granted by the commission³⁴. The authority can only be granted after an application for such has been made to the commission. And in taking the decision to grant or not, the commission is expected to have regard only to the likely effect of the takeover bid if successfully

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ See section 105 (1)

made, on the Nigerian economy as well as on any policy if the Federal Government on manpower and development.³⁵ Application for authority must be accompanied with a copy of the bid proposed.³⁶

The matters required to be stated by a takeover bid are stated section 107. Sections 108, 109, 110 and 111 made provisions for directors approval by resolution before any corporation could make takeover bid, dispatch of bid to shareholders, each director of the offeree company and the Commission, arrangement of funds for payment of shares by the offeror where consideration for the shares deposited is to be paid in money or partly money and directors circular respectively. Sections 113 and 114 deal with bids for all shares and bid for less than all shares respective Section 115 contains provisions applicable to every bid whether for all or for less than all . Section 117 is on the acquisition shares of dissenting shareholders while section 118 deals with situation where dissenting offeree makes election. Section 12 make general provisions as to payments while the rights of remaining shareholders are provided for in section 121. Section 122 makes provisions for offences and their sanctions.

ii. Procedures for Mergers

Procedures for mergers are dealt with under section 100 to 102 of ISA. Under this procedure where the whole or part of the undertaking or property of any company is to be transferred to another under a scheme proposed for a compromise, arrangement or reconstruction between two or more companies or the merger of any two or more companies, the court may on the application of any of the companies to be affected, order separate meetings of the companies in such manner as it may direct. If a majority representing not less than 3/4 in value of the shares of members being present and voting at each of the separate meetings agree to the scheme, it will be referred to the SEC and if approved will be sanctioned on the companies by the court on the application of any of the companies to be affected. The court may by its sanctioning order make provision for all or any of the matters enumerated in the Act.

³⁵ See section 105 (6)

³⁶ See section 105 (2)

(b) The Role of SEC

Section 99 (2) of the Act³⁷ subject every merger, acquisition or business combination between or among companies to prior review and approval of the commission. The commission is mandated to approve such application if and only if such acquisition, whether directly or indirectly, of the whole or any part of the equity , share capital or assets of another company is not likely to cause a substantial restraint of competition or tend to create a monopoly in any line of business enterprises or if the use of such acquired share by voting or granting of proxies or otherwise would not cause a substantial restraint of competition or tend to create a monopoly in any line of business enterprise³⁸.

The above section shall however not apply to holding companies acquiring shares solely for the purpose of investment and not for voting or otherwise cause or attempt to cause a substantial restraint of competition or tend to create a monopoly in any line of business enterprises³⁹. The section shall also not apply to transactions duly consummated pursuant to the authority given by any Federal Government owned agency under any statutory provision vesting such power in the agency.⁴⁰

The phrase "a substantial restraint of competition" has not received any judicial interpretation but the Security and Exchange Commission Guidelines on Mergers, Acquisitions and Combination list the factors necessary for granting approval for mergers and acquisition. This list predated ISA but remain applicable.

Moreover the Commission is empowered under section 258 and 262 to make rules and regulations for the purpose of giving effect to the provisions of the Act.

The factors listed by SEC guidelines are: the Geographic and Product Market⁴¹, Market Shares⁴² and Concentration Ratio⁴³.

³⁷ ISA, No 45 of 1999

³⁸ Section 99 (3) ISA

³⁹ Section 99 (4) ISA

⁴⁰ Section 99 (5) ISA

⁴¹ In determining whether competition might be restrained or a monopoly created as a result the proposed business re - organization, the SEC will identify the company's product (s) and the area

5. Competition Law

(a) Theory and Policy

Mergers and acquisitions should be carried out in a bid to enhance the competitiveness of a company and not to stifle competition. The consumer should be the main beneficiary. If a market is competitive in the sense that it contains a large number of firms, that each firm takes the price as given and entry and exit are cheap, then it can be shown that the resulting market equilibrium will be characterized by productive efficiency. Competition among firms will ensure that only the most efficient will survive and prices will reflect marginal costs. Moreover, if all markets are perfectly competitive, then those prices will be such as to sustain allocative efficiency; i.e. consumers (if they are well informed and rational) will be guided by them to choose combinations of goods which optimally meet their preferences⁴⁴. As with all types of restructuring, steps must be taken to soften the social impact of mergers and acquisitions. Competition policy is therefore necessary, provided it is based on the right assumptions, a global view, clear objectives and relevant criteria⁴⁵. The aim of competition policy is to protect consumers from the negative welfare consequences of excessive product market monopoly power. It affects three general areas: market

where it is manufactured or sold. The next point is to decide if a firm with a monopoly in that product within the area defined can raise prices profitably without being defeated by its customers purchasing other similar products or by the production of substitute products by competitors. If this cannot happen then these products compete in the same market

⁴² After identifying the products and geographic market, the next issue the SEC guidelines require is the determination of other participants in the market. Where the market share the merging or acquiring companies, which are measured by relating the annual sales of each company to the relevant product in the geographical market, will cause anti - competition i lead to a monopoly, mergers or take over will be refused by the commission.

⁴³ Once the market is established, the commission then goes to the calculation of market concentration, the general principle being that the more concentrated the market, the greater the likelihood that even a small increase in concentration would lead to a substantial restraint of competition or monopoly. Concentration is measured by combining the market shares of the major companies in the market. The number of the major companies in the market also determine the rate of concentration for example if two companies which are involved in a merger or takeover have 75% of the market, one can say that the market is highly concentrated. But if for instance 10 companies involved in the mergers have 75% of the market one can say or conclude that the market is not concentrated.

⁴⁴ See Competition and Competition Policy, Op cit at p. 2

⁴⁵ See Helmut O. Maucher; Op Cit at p. 154.

structure, business conducts and company performance. Competition policy relating to structure aims principally to thwart the development of unacceptably monopolized markets, for example through mergers. Legislation on conduct is concerned to prevent firms from acting to exploit market imperfections and performance can be controlled directly, for example through price controls⁴⁶.

Competition law differ from one economy to the other. A more fundamental conceptual distinction is between systems of competition law which focus upon dominance and those which focus upon market power. Market power depends upon the relative sizes or market share of firms, as well as upon other considerations such as entry barriers, the availability of substitutes, etc. Dominance on the other hand depends upon the absolute size of the supplier and its ability to determine outcomes for its trading partners.⁴⁷

It is sad to note that market competition⁴⁸ is not regarded as priority by government in the scheme of market reform.

(b) Competition Policy Globally

Currently on the global level there are ongoing discussions at the multilateral level by way of transatlantic antitrust dialogue to institute a global competition regime under the auspices of the World Trade Organization (WTO). Here, it is realized that even though all the major trading powers in the Organization for Economic Co - operation and Development (OECD) including Russia have antitrust regimes in their legal

⁴⁶ See Conclusions, being the concluding part of the book: Competition and Competition Policy, Printer Publishers Ltd, United Kingdom, 1993 by Saul Estrin and Martin Cave at pp 130 - 131

⁴⁷ See Competition and Competition Policy, Ibid at p. 6

⁴⁸ Sometime in 2000, the Federal government through the then Director - General of the Bu Public Enterprises (BPE) announced that it was in the process of introducing an antitrust regime in Nigeria by the enactment of a competition legislation. To prove its seriousness on this matter, the government through the National Council on Privatization (NCP) engaged the services of some legal consultants whose activities resulted in a draft legislation en titled: Federal Competition Bill. Nigerians with any experience and interest in this area of law were invited to make comments on this draft legislation (then posted on the internet), as part of a wider debate not just on antitrust but also on the overall liberalization of the Nigerian economy. Sadly, close to two years after the government indicated its intention on this matter and more than a year after the draft of the legislation, nothing has been heard on this project . See Nnamdi Dimgba; Nigeria's Competition Law: The Egg That Never Hatches, the Guardian, February 22, 2003, p. 13.

system to support the liberalization of their economies, a form of global coordination of those laws is necessary in order to realize the WTO's vision of fully liberalizing the global economy.

Furthermore, all of the ten accession countries to the European Union⁴⁹ for May 2004 were given the condition of liberalizing their economy before they could be considered suitable to join the Community. A major component of this condition was that they were to expose their economies to the force of competition.

It is significant that all these countries have by now put in place appropriate competition regimes in their economies, hence their eligibility to join the EU in May⁵⁰.

The American Anti-trust Regime dates back to 1890 when the Anti-trust Act of 1890 was passed by the Congress. The condition of the American people then was that of deep unrest in spite of having gotten rid of slavery. The country was in real danger of slavery that would result from aggregations of capital in the hands of a few individuals and corporations controlling for their own profit and advantages, exclusively the entire business of the country. To prevent this, the Act was passed. The Clayton Act and the Federal Trade Commissions Act of 1914 were later enacted as a response to perceived inadequacies both in the substantive scope and in the enforcement of the Sherman Act. The current mergers' guidelines was jointly issued by the U.S Justice Department and the Federal Trade Commission in 1992 and revised in 1997. The guidelines are designed primarily to articulate the analytical

⁴⁹ Articles 85 and 86 are the foundations of EC competition law concerning anti-competitive behaviour by enterprises. The former is directed at agreements or concerted practices between two or more enterprises. Whereas the latter is aimed at abusive behaviour by monopolies or firms with considerable economic power. These rules aim to achieve three objectives: (1) to prevent the erection of trade barriers consisting of restrictive agreements, and abuse of monopoly power; (2) to preserve effective competition as a foundation for the creation of the single market; and (3) to encourage efficiency and innovation and to lower prices. The EC competition laws were drafted and are implemented by the Commission and the Court of Justice with the overarching goal of market integration.

⁵⁰ See Nnamdi Dimgba; Nigeria's Competition Law: The Egg That Never Hatches. Op Cit . See: Williams R. Anderson & C Paul Rogers III; Anti-trust Law; Policy and Practice (3rd edition) Lexis Publishing, 1999 at pp 19-24. See also Appendix C - 3.

framework, the agency should apply in determining whether a merger is likely substantially to lessen competition.

(c) Competition Law in Transitional Economies

One of the fundamental steps taken by the former socialist states on transforming from centralized planning system to free market economy system is the passing of competition laws. Thus, the Polish parliament passed the Anti - Monopoly Law in February 1990 under which the anti - monopoly office was established as a government agency which is in charge of enforcement of anti - monopoly law. Hungary's Competition Act which was passed in 1990 came in to force on 1 January 1991. It covers questions of restrictive practices, abuse of dominant positions and control of mergers.

Czechoslovak Federal Assembly adopted the Competition Protection Act (CPA) on 30 January 1991 and it came into force on 1 March 1991. It applies to economic activities taking place abroad which have economic effects within the territory. The legislation applies equally to public and private enterprises and to most public utilities.

Recommendations and Conclusion

In this paper, we have examined the concepts of merge and acquisitions as a rising growth strategies in contemporary industrial co-operation worldwide having the aim of optimizing comparative strength and achieving synergy. We have also examined the various forms which business combinations could take vis-à-vis, vertical, horizontal and conglomerate integration. We have highlighted the arguments for and against business combinations and have argued that as attractive and beneficial merger and acquisitions could be, they could promote monopoly and anti-competitive practices which are detrimental to the larger society and not controlled or regulated by law . In this regard we have examined in particular the current legal and institutional framework for regulating business combinations in Nigeria.

It is submitted that section 99 (3) of ISA is grossly inadequate as it only relates to pre-mergers and acquisitions screening for the purpose of determining whether monopoly would result from such combinations. There is the need for a comprehensive

legislation on competition and a statutory agency to administer it. This agency should oversee all the activities and proposals of firms, (including merged and merging ones) with a view to detecting and prohibiting by sanctions, every anti-competitive practices⁵¹ including predatory pricings⁵², horizontal agreements among firms in the same market to fix prices or prohibit entry⁵³ as well as vertical agreements between a supplier and customer in the areas of retail price maintenances⁵⁴, exclusive dealings⁵⁵, territorial exclusivity⁵⁶, quantity discounts⁵⁷, tie- in sales⁵⁸, long – term supply contracts⁵⁹.

It is true that industrial mergers are informed solely by economic considerations such as determination to dislodge competitors, ensure efficiency and maximize profits and achieve greater influence and power for the management. The argument is that with the collapse of colonialism and the dawn of political freedom in Africa - the dumping ground for European, Asian and American products - there is the fear on the part of

⁵¹ See generally Saul Estrin and Martin Cave (ed) Competition and Competition Policy Printing Publishers Ltd., 1993 at p. 3

⁵² Predatory prong is normally defined as an attempt of firm (or group of firms) to lower its prices, drive a competitor out of the market, and then raise prices again. The argument against predatory pricing is that if a firm is threatened by many potential entrants, a policy of predatory pricing may be costly, as it will have to drive out not one but many competitors.

⁵³ If firms are able to form cartels in this way, they can raise prices as high as those which would be charged by a monopolist without any compensating advantages in the form of economies of scale or rationalized production. They are thus highly unlikely to promote efficiency, and in most jurisdictions they are prohibited, or allowed only in exceptional cases. Agreement that firms to share Rand D costs create a more difficult dilemma because of the public good aspect of scientist knowledge. For this reason, co - operation in basic or strategic research is sometimes permitted, even though agreements to share near-market research and development costs are often prohibited.

⁵⁴ Where the manufacturer imposes upon the retailer a minimum price at which a product can be sold

⁵⁵ Where a retailer undertakes to sell only one manufacturer's product, and not the output of rival firms

⁵⁶ Where a particular retailer is given sole rights to sell the products of a manufacturer in a specified area.

⁵⁷ Where retailers receive progressively larger discounts the more of a given manufacturer's product they sell - this obviously gives them an incentive at the margin to push one manufacturer's product at the expense of another's.

⁵⁸ Restraint which require the retailer to take good X if he or she is to be supplied with good Y - by this means, a manufacturer can extend a monopoly in one market into another, and discourage new entry (by forcing a prospective entrant to come into both markets simultaneously)

⁵⁹ These bind a retailer to a supplier and often can only be terminated by the retailer at great cost

former colonial masters that unless a subtle mode of domination is hoisted on Africa, the continent may soon achieve economic/industrial liberation as well, thus abandoning the west and other super powers with their mass produced goods.

In order to forestall this seeming economic calamity, foreign conglomerates have resorted to mergers in order to cut costs, strengthen their financial and administrative base as we as create common platforms for formulating and executing policies which will not only perpetuate their economic and political hold on Africa and the entire world, but will most important streamline their operations.

With mergers therefore, hitherto separate organization which used to have different staff, spend greater funds on their salaries and other overheads and incur more expenses on social responsibility programmes etc. will now operate under one umbrella and thus employ less staff, spend less resources of their retained staff and engage in fewer and hence cheaper projects.

For this reason, African governments should critically examine every single case of acquisition deals with a view to ascertaining whether it is in the best interest of their economies or not. A situation where some firms simply merge overseas but remain separate and independent in this country calls for concerning Government is hereby urged to find out whether this state of affairs is in anyway inimical to the Nigerian economy.

In Nigeria if we must liberalise our economy, then we should begin by setting our basic right. The only solid foundation upon which any genuine market liberalization programme must stand is a functioning competition regime⁶⁰.

⁶⁰ See Kingsley Onwukwe: Privatisation and Competition in the Nigerian Economic. See Thisday, Tuesday September 23, 2003, p. 43 vol. 9, no. 2075.